

SA-Score: Measuring Data Sharing Effort through the Lens of Open Science and the FAIR Principles

Introduction: The Need for a Transformative Metric in DRO Sharing

In scientific publications, openly sharing research findings, analysis, data, and other digital research objects (DROs) is crucial for advancing knowledge. And yet, the activity of **sharing** is not a normative behavior for all researchers, and this hinders the acceleration of science and innovation. Researchers are rewarded for publications that are highly cited, but not for sharing critical DROs used to arrive at those findings.

Our novel metric, the **SA-Score**, encourages and rewards DRO sharing and attribution that is transparent, community-driven, and adaptable. It focuses on researcher behavior and DRO resource (e.g., repository) infrastructure that rewards all contributors (e.g., producers, curators, stewards) of high quality DROs providing visibility and incentives for reuse.

Researchers and research contributors spend considerable time preparing DROs that are often siloed, inadequately cited, or incompatible with evolving infrastructures¹. Meanwhile, DRO resources, scholarly communication systems, discipline communities, and institutions lack coordinated mechanisms for tracking appropriate sharing and attribution practices and rewarding their adoption. Traditional metrics like citation counts or journal impact factors do not recognize the multifaceted labor behind effective DRO sharing and attribution. The SA-Score closes those gaps by building on existing systems and practices, making implementation feasible. By design, this metric reflects the collaborative nature of modern science. It acknowledges the roles of DRO contributors, resources, and users, while introducing quantifiable, flexible indicators measuring and promoting desired behavior. It also encourages integration with emerging standards for tenure and promotion. Crucially, the SA-Score supports the FAIR Principles² and adaptation to emerging frameworks addressing historical exclusions such as the CARE Principles³, Traditional Knowledge and Biocultural Labels⁴, and other local/national-level standards.

A multi-disciplinary group of researchers, contributors, and science advocates

The challenge of building a new metric to improve and value DRO sharing and reuse has many facets, and to address these, we have assembled a team with exceptional breadth and depth of expertise in data sharing. The team comprises individuals from leading research institutions, government agencies, and global organizations—including NASA, NIST, the University of California, JHU, MIT, AGU, and the Allen Institute (Team Roster, **Supplemental Table 2**). These 50+ experts span disciplines including biohealth, earth, environment, atmospheric, ocean, computer science, law, information science, materials, humanities, and economics. Their combined experience includes leadership in developing and implementing data infrastructures, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), and metadata standards; advancing FAIR and CARE principles; and shaping DRO sharing policy through global initiatives like the Research Data Alliance (RDA), FORCE11, and the Research Software Alliance. Importantly, this group also brings strong representation in critical areas: established data practices⁵, data sovereignty, open access publishing, and trusted data systems evaluation as well as critical DROs. Interdisciplinary composition and demonstrated leadership positions this team as the ideal collaborative body to design comprehensive, scalable, and sustainable DRO-sharing solutions that meet the advancing challenges of the scientific endeavor and broader society⁶.

Innovation: A Behavioral Model for FAIR-Aligned DRO Sharing and Attribution

Desired behaviors surrounding DRO usage includes sharing DROs effectively and attributing DRO contributors throughout the DRO lifecycle, ensuring acknowledgement of, and credit for the work and roles required for a robust DRO ecosystem. These behaviors also reinforce use of appropriate resources as **designated by the relevant community** in making DROs easy to find, access, explore, integrate, cite, and reuse. Previous indices and measures have emphasized building individual reputations in closed systems at the cost of poor societal appreciation for the public benefits of science and lack of public understanding of the complex teamwork and community and shared resources that constitute science⁷.

Our approach establishes a score that incentivizes the researcher's desired share and attribution behaviors, contributes to the future soundness of the research ecosystem, and invites individual discipline communities to participate in defining the desired criteria. Our conceptual innovation provides unifying guidance, accountability, and coordination to existing infrastructure that already collates key indicators. The SA-Score model scales across disciplines, repositories, and funding systems by focusing on shared behaviors and infrastructures while partnering with discipline communities around shared resources and incorporating community preferences into the criteria. One concrete example is the BICAN (US-BRAIN Cell Census) repositories need to support rapid sharing and progressive refinement, while SPARC (NIH Common Fund) rewards complete metadata with their datasets.

Community-Designated DRO Resources

DRO resources are necessary infrastructure in the research ecosystem, currently supporting desired research contributor behaviors and providing services which directly allow DROs to be found in context, and to impact the quality of sharing. Community-designated DRO resources can redefine research, as demonstrated using Protein Data Bank in the development of AlphaFold, or enable the aggregation of small underpowered "long-tail" study output into highly powered datasets⁸. Regardless, DRO resources are inconsistently recognized in current evaluation measures. Author attribution of DROs in research products and results (e.g., manuscripts, derived datasets, models) will enable counts as part of the scholarly impact of DRO resources.

While lists of repositories are available from some journals and societies as well as the NIH sharing website, the processes for determining community-designated DRO resources must be transparent and must incorporate community governance including global representation. This can be accomplished by convening stakeholders through professional and scholarly societies, funders, and international bodies such as the RDA. Community convenings will establish processes to designate DRO resources and standard practices for metadata and formats in alignment with DRO-type, research area, national/regional laws, and institutional guidance, and may use repository certification criteria (e.g., CoreTrustSeal) and US Repository Characteristics⁹ to inform the designation criteria. These designated DRO resources along with adequate context¹⁰ for each DRO build a "trusted" resource. An individual selecting a community-designated DRO resource leverages the expertise and services for making their DRO as FAIR and well-documented as possible. DRO resource lists must be stored in an open, agreed-upon place; e.g., [RRIDs](#), [FAIRSharing](#), [Re3Data](#), or [DataCite](#). A Sample DRO Resource Evaluation Checklist (**Figure 2**) can be used to get a community started with their decision-making process.

Proposed DRO Sharing Score (S-Score), Attribution Score (A-Score), combined SA-Score

The combined SA-Score represents an individual's DRO **sharing** (S-Score) and **attribution** (A-Score) behavior. It indicates use and incentivizes use of community-designated, FAIR-aligned resources, and metadata standards. Having two composite sub-scores provides more flexibility and interpretability to the combined SA-Score, which quantifies the following practices:

- Depositing DROs in community-designated DRO resources, for **sharing**.
- Describing DROs with robust metadata including scientific protocols, data dictionaries, and common data elements, for more effective **sharing**.
- Using PIDs for research contributors, DROs, grants, funders, infrastructure providers, and institutions to support automated **attribution**, PID graphs, linking, is **sharing** best practice.
- Linking DROs to other scholarly outputs by citing DROs appropriately, supports **attribution**.

The incentivized behavior starts with researchers using the recommended DRO resource designated by their community and providing the recommended robust metadata with each DRO. Behavior needs to also include proper DRO attribution. **Using the best possible DRO resource is the single most impactful decision that contributes significantly to how discoverable, understandable, and reusable the digital object can be.** Community-designated resources that only include services for ORCID integration and PID registration provide the bare minimum

of DRO sharing support. Additional services such as support for curating robust metadata, ease the burden of understanding the DRO, increase potential reuse, improve AI model training¹¹, and allow for aggregated analysis that can lead to important scientific innovations not currently possible with current DRO sharing behaviors. The effort in providing robust metadata is a small

investment compared with expanded future use.

Calculating Sharing and Attribution Scores for Researchers

Sharing score (S-Score): Shows whether a DRO is shared along with robust metadata. Once it has a registered PID, it can be associated with a paper, technical report, or cited in secondary products. It is based on 3 items assessed for each DRO:

- **Depositing DROs in the best possible DRO resource as established by the relevant community.** Community designated resource used: Score = 1; DRO resource that is not community designated: Score = 0.5; A location that is NOT a repository nor designated resource (e.g., GitHub or personal website) used: Score = 0.
- **Using an ORCID for all DRO contributors.** ORCID is present for all: Score = 1; Missing ORCID: Score = 0; DRO contributors with intentionally no ORCID are not penalized.
- **Describing DROs with robust metadata supporting understanding and reuse, as established by the relevant community.** Robust metadata: Score = 1; Essential metadata supporting discovery: Score = 0.5; Essential metadata not present: Score = 0.

The total score for a DRO is the sum of the scores for the 3 items; the highest score is a 3 (three) which can be mapped to a qualitative scale: 3 = exceptional, 2.5 - 2 = good, 1.5 - fair, 1 - 0.5 = poor, 0 = very poor. For a collection of DROs (e.g., from a researcher, institution, repository) the S-Score is calculated as an average of the scores of all DROs. The overall S-score can be averaged for a bounded time (e.g., last 5 years).

Attribution score (A-Score): Shows whether DROs that are used to support the research findings are attributed in scholarly work or other DRO. It is based on one item assessed for each research output (article, report, secondary dataset):

- **DROs are given proper attribution and linked.** Scholarly work cites a DRO: Score = 1; scholarly work does not cite a DRO: Score = 0. For each research output the highest score for attribution is a 1 (one). This approach mitigates any gain from a scholarly work having many cited DROs.

For a collection of research outputs, the overall A-Score is calculated as an average score. The overall score can be for a bounded time (e.g., last 5 years).

Sharing and Attribution Score (SA-Score) can be calculated for an individual researcher or at a higher level (e.g. institution, repository, topic), by calculating their average S-Score for their datasets and average A-Score for their research outputs (articles, reports, secondary datasets, etc.) for the same time period and adding them together: SA-Score = Average S-Score + Average A-Score.

Feasibility

The SA-Score is an eminently implementable metric with current technology and available infrastructure. Our team has piloted elements of the approach and demonstrated success and

feasibility (**Figure 1, 2**), particularly where the approach relies on current PID infrastructures that exist at scale (e.g., DOIs, [ORCID](#), [DataCite](#), [RRIDs](#), RORs) and existing sharing and attribution leading practices. For broad adoption, the sharing of digital objects must be meaningful, appropriate, and guided by the needs of discipline communities and context of how the digital object supports specific research areas.

The implementation challenge is to create a scalable and replicable framework for communities to self-organize and establish governance and process as demonstrated by the new AGU Technical Committee for remote sensing instrumentation and observations¹². The feasibility of the SA-Score requires dedicated coordination and convening of discipline communities, with broad involvement of stakeholders from across the research ecosystem (**Supplemental Table 1**) ensuring that the DRO resource- and standard practice- designation processes are transparent, sustainable, acceptable to the respective communities, and appropriate to their needs. All stakeholders need to participate in building guidelines, training, and ongoing improvements¹³. These community convenings are also necessary to close existing gaps in coordination such as communities using or defining a DRO taxonomy; publishers and reference managers¹⁴ being accountable for ensuring that citations for DROs are properly handled and machine-actionable; institutions and disciplines incorporating the score into current research evaluation systems; and DRO-resources providing in their DRO schema a way to be identified and connected through a PID graph, e.g., ROR, RRID, DOI, FAIR-Sharing.

Designated resources need to be recognized and rewarded for their contribution in supporting sharing of DROs, improving services they provide, increase in DRO reuse, sustainability, and fostering the importance of being a “trusted” community resource.

Impact of DRO resources is derived from the attribution/citation of DROs

Our SA-Score recognizes that DRO resources are critical for sharing, linking digital objects to contributors, and for the transparency and potential reuse of DROs in the research ecosystem. This score incentivizes the behavior of researchers and their teams to use designated DRO repositories and give proper attribution. This in turn rewards contributors to the creation of the DRO, reinforces the community resources as a place to find relevant DROs, and recognizes a DRO as a contribution to the scientific record.

Discipline communities will be able to compare the usage of designated DRO resources over time, DRO reuse, and provide meaningful feedback to funders on the impact DRO resources have to their community. We need the designated DRO resources to be valued, sustainable, and trusted elements of each research community. Their impact on innovation, time-to-science, and speed-of-translation is immeasurable with 10.2 billion euro as the estimated cost of **not** making data FAIR¹⁵.

We have identified the community-designated DRO repository, its capabilities, and its community-endorsed role as the crucial component for supporting researchers and teams in addressing the needs of the 21st Century. We can no longer “hunt” for data, “wonder” if software is usable, or “flip through” thousands of supplements to find remnants of incomplete datasets and “miss out on” negative data.

Conclusion

The proposed SA-score represents a substantial advance over existing models by integrating community-driven decision making and technical standards, with behavioral incentives. It strengthens trust in science by promoting transparency, value in DROs as a scientific contribution, and shared accountability. It recognizes supporting DRO resources, such as repositories, as core contributors and provides a clear path, led by research communities, for researchers, publishers, secondary service providers, and institutions to engage in responsible data and digital object sharing practices.

Supplement

Table 1: A summary of research ecosystem stakeholders, feasible actions, and existing support for implementation is provided below. Members of each stakeholder group have demonstrated technological feasibility by improving or addressing these gaps.

Stakeholder	Feasible Actions	Existing Support	Gap to Address
DRO Contributors/ Researchers	Share DROs; Attribute DROs	Repositories, ORCID, ROR, DataCite DOI registration.	Training, cultural shift, access to community-designated DRO resources and metadata information, consistent use of community-designated DRO resources.
DRO Resource (e.g., repository)	Provide visible, and machine-actionable indication on the webpage that this repository is a designated DRO resource. Adopt and harmonize metadata schemas, implement PIDs, citation standards, outreach, and adherence to community designated standards. Provide streamlined workflows that make it easy for researchers to share their DROs through these resources. Make metadata machine-actionable.	NIH Repository List ; TRUST Principles, CoreTrustSeal Certification, DataCite membership, re3data schema, Science on Schema.org , US Repository Characteristics ⁹ .	Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior. Implementation and usage tracking. Services that meet the support/curation needs of researchers, quality validation. Use of PIDs. Workflow support. Machine-actionable metadata.
PID Registry Entities and Agencies	Support DRO citation and linking to scholarly publication. Update “related publication” metadata for DROs.	DOI.org, Crossref, DataCite	Consistency in implementation.
Scholarly societies	Support the work of discipline communities and regular review of DRO resources and standard	Annual meetings; virtual workshops	Help convene community meetings and work efforts to establish community-

Stakeholder	Feasible Actions	Existing Support	Gap to Address
	<p>practice designation. Promote use of community-designated resources and metadata. Adopt DRO designated resources and standards in society journals.</p>		<p>designated resources and metadata. Sustained community coordination and incentives. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.</p>
<p>DRO Resource Designation Host</p>	<p>Host and manage the designated resources (e.g., repositories) for each community. Provide transparent access to the DRO designated resources, easy search, machine actionable, version controlled, transparent.</p>	<p>DataCite, re3data, FAIRSharing, OpenAIRE, World Data System, NIH Repository List.</p>	<p>Sustained hosting of the community designated DRO resource. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.</p>
<p>Publishers</p>	<p>Require DRO citation in manuscripts; ensure DRO citations follow author guidelines, are inclusive of what was used for the research findings and formatted to be machine-actionable in downstream services.</p>	<p>FORCE11, Crossref, CHORUS, Journal Production, Guidance for Software and Data Citations¹⁶.</p>	<p>Better compliance mechanisms. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.</p>
<p>Journal editors, reviewers, and staff</p>	<p>Editors, reviewers, and staff of scholarly journals and other communication are the gatekeepers of following leading practices and standards. Ensure understanding of leading practices and standards for DRO availability statements, citations, and in-text citation guidelines for the relevant communities.</p>	<p>FORCE11, Crossref, CHORUS, Journal Production, Guidance for Software and Data Citations¹⁶. COPE resources.</p>	<p>Access to support systems to help ensure best possible sharing and attribution behavior.</p>
<p>Funders</p>	<p>Align funding criteria with good DRO practices.</p>	<p>NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy,</p>	<p>Integration into review/award systems.</p>

Stakeholder	Feasible Actions	Existing Support	Gap to Address
		Horizon Europe mandates, NERC data management policy (UK), WMO policy, IOC policy	Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.
Reference Managers	Support DRO citation formats and PID imports.	Zotero, EndNote, Mendeley—partial support ¹⁴ .	Correct deficiencies and enable validation. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.
Secondary Service Provider	An DRO resource that provides added value to researchers and the research ecosystem making an existing DRO more interoperable and more reusable, usually for further communities.	IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC) repositories (climate); NOAA’s Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) hosted on Stanford’s Redivis platform ; climate services	Ensure documentation of provenance, resources, and giving attribution to those supporting resources. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.
DRO Tool Providers	This is a broad category for any type of DRO tool to support the research ecosystem.	DMPTool.org ; Scholix.org	Incorporate updated leading practices. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.
Institutions	Reward researchers following and contributing to DRO designated resources and standards. Reward discipline communities developing and managing DRO designated resources and standards. Reward DRO resources for supporting researchers with the best possible sharing of DROs.	ORCID assertions, ROR links.	Establish reward. Formal integration into hiring/tenure/promotion. Encourage/prompt SA-Score behavior.

Figure 1: Feasibility of repositories asking authors for proper citation. Here, please find the [SPARC repository dataset](#) landing page asking authors to cite the RRID for SPARC along with the dataset. Below, please find the [data availability section](#) of a paper citing version 1 of this dataset, as instructed.

Abstract	About	Cite	Files	Gallery	References	Versions
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Dataset Citation

How to cite this dataset

To promote reproducibility and give credit to your colleagues who publish their data, we recommend the following practices for citing a SPARC Dataset. Please acknowledge the contributors, cite the dataset(s) that contained the files that you used, and include the SPARC Portal DOI & RRID in your publications. To make it easy, the SPARC Portal provides the full data citation, including the option of different citation formats below, to incorporate into your manuscript. For more Information, including examples of how to include multiple datasets and repositories, please see our [Help page](#)

Materials and Methods

Data and experimental protocols associated with this study are available on the SPARC Portal (RRID: SCR_017041): <https://doi.org/10.26275/wh9h-tbew>

Data Availability Statement

Data are publicly available on the SPARC Portal (RRID:SCR_017041) at the following the URL: <https://doi.org/10.26275/wh9h-tbew>

References

APA

Bizanti, A. (Gigi), Zhang, Y., Osanlouy, M., Heal, M., Chen, J., & Cheng, Z. (2023). Topographical mapping of sympathetic postganglionic innervation of the mouse heart (Version 1) [Dataset]. SPARC Portal. <https://doi.org/10.26275/WH9H-TBEW>

Data availability

The original high quality figures and data associated with this study⁸³, are available through the SPARC Portal (RRID: SCR_017041) under a CC-BY 4.0 license. [10.26275/s2qj-9ggp](https://doi.org/10.26275/s2qj-9ggp). Additional data analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Figure 2: A Sample DRO Resource Evaluation Checklist. We expect this to be acceptable and feasible as the repositories represented within our group have implemented some of these practices.

<i>DRO Resource Evaluation Items</i>
<p>Sample Minimal Checklist</p> <p>This checklist may guide and inform research communities in identifying appropriate DRO resources for their community.</p> <p>ORCID for DRO contributors</p> <p>PID for each DRO, e.g., DOI/ARK/Handle/a.o., hdl,</p> <p>PID for affiliations/organizations (ROR), funder (ROR / Funder ID), grant (Grant IDs, research project (RaiDs), physical sample (IGSN), and instruments (RRIDs).</p> <p>Documented schema like Dublin Core, DataCite, and schema.org Available of machine-readable metadata and schema that adheres to community standards.</p> <p>Pushes to data aggregator Pushes information to ORCID (about an individual) or Datacite (about the DRO)</p> <p>Aligns with desired repository characteristics (e.g., CoreTrustSeal, TRUST, the US Repository Characteristics⁹</p> <p>Data formats and consistency guidance: Provides guidelines for consistent data formatting and structuring, ensures that shared data are usable. Guidelines may be parsed/enforced by machine, e.g., BIDS</p> <p>Content curation and/or metadata verification provided</p> <p>DRO citations formatted for compatibility with publishers and reference managers. Complete citations include repository ID (e.g., RRID) and the DRO PID. (Figure 1)</p> <p>Landing pages for each DRO, with both human- and machine-accessible information¹⁷</p> <p>Archiving / Versioning Policies supporting transparency, long-term access (e.g., LOCKSS/CLOCKSS/Portico), and sustainability¹⁸.</p> <p>Outreach and education e.g., office hours, hosting workshops or dataset-specific community engagement.</p>

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Glossary

Item	Description
AGU	American Geophysical Union
community-designated	This label is applied to DRO resources, standards, practices, etc. that have been identified by the relevant community using processes that are transparent, sustainable, acceptable to the respective communities, and appropriate to their needs.
Digital Research Objects	Datasets, data systems, software, code, models, digital reference to physical samples, images, audio, etc.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DRO	Digital Research Object
DRO contributors	These are the people instrumental in creating, producing, preparing, cleaning, stewarding, and/or curating, the DRO. Other terms used: authors, creators, producers.
DRO resource	For the purpose of this document, we mean “repository”. There are other DRO resources of interest for FAIR DROs such as ontologies, taxonomies, and vocabularies. The community-designated metadata standards will need to account for this.
essential metadata	This is metadata that is optimal for finding a DRO. It typically includes the link to the DRO, title, contributors, and perhaps a few more metadata elements ¹⁹
FAIRsharing	https://fairsharing.org/ “A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies.”
JHU	Johns Hopkins University
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
relevant community	These are groups of researchers and other research ecosystem stakeholders at the optimal level of granularity to establish designated resources and metadata standards for the types of DROs used in that research. There will be overlap between communities. Professional societies and international DRO groups can help with the overlap and cross community coordination, while supporting sustained accountability and governance.
robust metadata	This is metadata that is optimal for understanding and reuse of a DRO. The term “robust” is not common to all disciplines. Relevant communities determine what “robust” means for their community.

Item	Description
ROR	https://ror.org/ an organization identifier and “a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organizations”
RRID	A persistent unique identifier “designed to help researchers cite the key ... resources used to produce their scientific findings.” https://www.rrids.org/current-project
Secondary service provider	Provides services that make DROs reusable for further user communities, (e.g., NASA Data Processing Levels 2-4 ²⁰). There are many players in this role in the climate community, e.g., IPCC , Rolling Deck to Repositories .

Table 2: Team Roster

Team members are considered individuals when participating in this challenge.

Team Roster

Name	Job Title	Career Stage	Short Biography	ORCID	Affiliation
Co-Chairs					
Shelley Stall	Vice President Open Science Leadership	Senior	Shelley Stall is the Vice President for the American Geophysical Union's (AGU) Open Science Leadership Program. Shelley received her BA in Mathematics and Computer Science from Shippensburg University and MBA with a focus on Production Operations from Ball State University. Shelley is a globally recognized advocate for preserving and sharing data and software in support of transparent, and open scholarship. She serves on the Board on Research Data and Information of the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine and the Roundtable on Aligning Incentives for Open Scholarship. She is the co-chair of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Organizational Assembly, and leads working groups focused on the FAIR Data Maturity Model, Complex Citations, and discipline-specific work in the Earth Space and Environmental Sciences Community of Practice.	0000-0003-2926-8353	American Geophysical Union
Anita Bandrowski	Co-Founder, CEO SciCrunch Inc. RRIDs.org lead, Specialist, University of California at San Diego	Senior	BS, PhD in physiological psychology studying learning and epilepsy models in neocortical cells, genome curator for Celera Inc, genomic pipeline architect Human Longevity, lead for Neuroscience Information Framework, lead for RRIDs.org, Co-founder and CEO of SciCrunch Inc. Dr. Bandrowski's experience is strongly rooted in the biological sciences, but her post graduate research centers on data, open data, and reproducibility. From the human genome project to aggregating the world's largest compendium of research resources like antibodies and databases, to getting a hundred thousand authors to cite them, she leads projects to not to simply define, but to solve critical research problems.	0000-0002-5497-0243	RRIDs.org , The University of California at San Diego
Amy Numberger	Program Head, Data Management Services	Mid	BS Biochemistry, MS Information studies. Ms. Nurnberger worked in the biotech and pharmaceutical industries for over a decade, and is currently mid-career in higher education information services. Ms. Numberger is a member of several professional societies and scientific boards, including the Vivli External Adviosry Board and the Research Data Alliance where she is a member of Council and a co-chair of the Evaluation of Research, and Education and Training on Handling Research Data groups.	0000-0002-5931-072X	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Members in Alphabetical Order					
Deg Agarwal	Computer Senior Scientist and Engineer	Senior	Dr. Deborah Agarwal is a Senior Scientist and the Data Science and Technology Department (http://dst.lbl.gov), Head at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL). Dr. Agarwal's current research focuses on developing computational tools to enable scientists to more effectively organize and use their data to understand and mitigate climate change. The Data Science and Technology Department personnel are involved in data analytics and data management projects across the sciences. Dr. Agarwal is also the lead of the Environmental Systems Science Data Infrastructure for a Virtual Ecosystem (ESS-DIVE) data repository.	0000-0001-5045-2396	Lawrence Berkely National Laboratory
Jane Anderson	Associate Professor of Anthropology and Museum Studies and a Global Fellow in the Engelberg Center for Innovation Law and Policy	Senior	Dr. Jane Anderson is Associate Professor of Anthropology and Museum Studies and a Global Fellow in the Engelberg Center for Innovation Law and Policy in the Law School at New York University. Jane has a Ph.D. in Law from the Law School at University of New South Wales in Australia. Their work is focused on the philosophical and practical problems for intellectual property law and the protection of Indigenous/traditional knowledge resources and cultural heritage in support of Indigenous knowledge and data sovereignty.	0000-0002-3304-0477	New York University
James Ayliffe	Marine Data Manager	Mid	Master's degree in marine science with over 10 year's experience as a marine data manager. Experience includes building and managing data flows for blue skies research data in addition to data for policy and assessments. Complementary focus has been on the importance of provenance and traceability of scientific data to support the scientific reasoning and the scientific method.	0000-0002-7363-5029	British Oceanographic Data Centre, National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool

Wade Bishop	Professor	Mid	Wade Bishop is a Professor at the School of Information Sciences at the University of Tennessee-Knoxville. His research focus is on Research Data Management, Data Discovery, Geographic Information Science, as well as the study of data occupations, education, and training. He has other research expertise that includes physical access for users to U.S. public libraries (using Geographic information Systems (GIS)) and the evaluation of many other services and resources in academic and public libraries	0000-0002-5022-2707	University of Tennessee-Knoxville
Ian Bruno	Director of Data Initiatives	Senior	Ian has a background in chemistry and informatics, and decades of experience in research data management, discovery, and reuse—primarily at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC). As a software engineer, he contributed to the development of tools for searching, analysing, and visualising crystallographic data. He has also managed a range of technical and scientific projects and teams. In his current role, Ian is responsible for establishing strategies that will make CCDC's data more discoverable and reusable across wider scientific communities. A specific focus is on the adoption and development of community guidelines, standards and sustainability models that can support these aims globally. Ian is an active participant in projects and working groups of international scientific organisations including the InChI Trust, IUPAC, IUCr, CODATA, and the RDA.	0000-0003-4901-9936	Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre
Justin Buck	Principal Robotics Engineer	Mid	PhD in civil and construction engineering specialising in polar oceanography and fluid dynamics. Sixteen years data management experience in the British Oceanographic Data centre focusing on environmental research data collected by marine autonomous robotic systems. A decade of experience on the challenges faced by the research community on data attribution and credit. One year of experience as a principal robotics engineer working on the digital and data infrastructure with emerging technologies (including AI) to enable new approaches in ocean observation for the research community. Member of international steering and coordination groups including: International Oceanographic Commission (IOC) Ocean Best Practice System (OBPS) steering team, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Oceans Coordination Group (OCG) data task team, and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) complex citations working group.	0000-0002-3587-4889	National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool
Todd Carpenter	Executive Director	Senior	Since 2006, Todd Carpenter has served as Executive Director of the National Information Standards Organization (NISO). Prior to joining NISO, Todd held management positions at BioOne, the Johns Hopkins University Press, Energy Intelligence Group, and Haworth Press. He has served on the Boards of several community organizations, including as President of FORCE11, as Vice President of Baltimore County Public Library Foundation, as Treasurer of the Book Industry Study Group and as Treasurer of the Society for Scholarly Publishing. Todd received a BA in German and philosophy from Syracuse University and MS in marketing engineering from the Johns Hopkins University.	0000-0002-8320-0491	National Information Standards Organization (NISO)
Christy Caudill	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Early	Dr. Christy Caudill is an Earth, Data, and Systems Scientist working at the intersection of digital technologies and data science decolonization. Caudill is a Research Fellow at the Geomatics and Cartographic Research Centre (GCRC) at Carleton University and a Sustainability Studies Graduate Program Adjunct Professor and Lecturer at Trent University. She is an active science-policy advocate with the United Nations Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). Christy holds grants with the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), is a participating team member European Space Agency (ESA) space missions, and has received outstanding achievement awards from NASA and the Canadian Space Agency (CSA).	0000-0003-2587-1147	Carleton University, Trent University

Zack Chandler	Executive Director (Open Source Projects Office)	Mid	A technologist, service designer, and open science advocate, I have spent most of my career at Stanford University, starting with academic computing in Stanford Libraries (ATS Program), then a 5-year tour with University IT (Web Services), after which I founded a new group within the Office of the Vice Provost and Dean of Research (VPDOR - Research IT & Innovation). My current role is to help advance the practice of open science with the Center for Open and Reproducible Science (SDS - CORES), and by participating in national networks such as HELIOS Open. Before Stanford, I was the Director of the Language Resource Center (LRC) at Colby College in Maine, where I worked with a delightful and brilliant cadre of faculty and students in building the LRC into a full featured media lab, built reusable learning objects, exploring creative commons licensing, and home grown content through constructivist approaches to language learning.	0000-0003-2402-9839	Stanford University
Joan Damerow	Geological Project Scientist	Mid	Joan is an environmental scientist with a diverse background in environmental assessment, remediation, and geoscience sampling; biological monitoring; freshwater ecology; and informatics. She is the community engagement lead for the ESS-DIVE data repository for Earth and environmental sciences data. And is an expert in sample data management and interdisciplinary data. She leads the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) Physical Samples Curation Cluster, which provides a forum for the community supporting physical samples in the Earth, space, and environmental sciences.	0000-0003-2601-5043	Lawrence Berkely National Laboratory
Robert Downs	Senior Digital Archivist and Acting Head of Cyberinfrastructure and Informatics Research and Development (Center for International Earth Science Information Network (CIESIN))	Senior	Dr. Robert R. Downs serves as the senior digital archivist and acting head of cyberinfrastructure and informatics research and development at CIESIN, the Center for International Earth Science Information Network, a research and data center of the Earth Institute of Columbia University. He is an elected member of the CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, co-chair of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) Data Working Group, and co-chair of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Interest Group on Repository Platforms for Research Data. He also serves as a co-chair of the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) Information Quality Cluster, as an At-Large Member of the EarthCube Council of Data Facilities, on the Editorial Board of the International Science Council (ISC) Committee on Data (CODATA) Data Science Journal, and on the Governance Committee for ESIP.	0000-0002-8595-5134	Columbia University
Ruth Duerr	Research Scholar	Senior	I'm a generalist with interests in music, art, science, sustainable agriculture, data, and policy. I've been actively involved in Earth, space, and information sciences for decades. I currently chair the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) Finance Committee and serve on the ESIP Board. I've held leadership positions in groups like NASA's Earth Observing System Operations Working Group and the Research Data Alliance's e-Preservation and Domain Repositories Interest Groups. I previously served as the elected Secretary for the Earth and Space Science Informatics Focus Group of the American Geophysical Union (AGU) and was its President with a seat on the AGU Council. I currently serve on the interim council of the newly formed Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship 2.0 (RIIS - pronounced rise).	0000-0003-4808-4736	RIIS 2.0
David Elbert	Faculty Research Scientist	Senior	More than 20 years experience in data intensive science, including neutron, photon, and electron data integration; DataOps; cyberinfrastructure development; and AI-applications for experimental analysis and optimization. Co-developer of the Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs) concept integrating robotics with AI for laboratory autonomy and the NASA IMQCAM runnable Digital Twin Environment. He is Lead-PI for the NSF FAIR and Open Science Materials Research Coordination Network and a Co-Founder and Executive Council Member of the Materials Research Data Alliance (MaRDA).	0000-0002-2292-180X	Johns Hopkins University

Ixchel M. Faniel	Senior Research Scientist	Senior	Ixchel M. Faniel is a Senior Research Scientist at OCLC. She has extensive experience examining how researchers manage, share, evaluate and reuse data and identifying the implications for data producers, curators and repositories. In related research, Ixchel has examined academic libraries' experiences offering research data management programs, studied science, technology, engineering, and mathematics students from grade school to graduate school as they identify and judge the credibility of digital resources, and investigated the ways academic libraries can improve the discoverability of open access publications. Ixchel's research has been funded by the National Science Foundation, Institute of Museum and Library Services, and National Endowment for the Humanities.	0000-0001-7302-5936	OCLC
Adam Ferguson	Professor and Co-Director, UCSF Brain and Spinal Injury Center	Senior	Adam R. Ferguson, MS, PhD is Co-Director Brain and Spinal Injury at the Zuckerberg San Francisco General Hospital, and Professor of Neurological Surgery in the Weill Institute for Neurosciences at UCSF. He directs a team of researchers performing a hybrid of bench neuroscience and translational data science, supported by grants from the NIH, VA, DoD, DARPA, Department of Energy and non-profits. He also directs data sharing efforts through the Open Data Commons for TBI (odc-tbi.org) and SCI (odc-sci.org), major NIH-Supported Repositories for Neurotrauma. He has authored 250+ peer-reviewed scientific papers across bench science, data science, and clinical neurotrauma research.	0000-0001-7102-1608	The University of California, San Francisco
Jeffrey Grethe	Associate Director Center for Research in Biological Systems and co-Director of the FAIR Data Informatics Laboratory; Department of Neurosciences, University of California, San Diego	Senior	B.S. in Applied Mathematics, PhD in neurosciences with a focus on neuroinformatics and computational modeling from the University of Southern California. After a post-doc in non-invasive human imaging (PET, MRI, fMRI) at Emory University joined the fMRI Data Center (fMRIDC) at Dartmouth College. At the fMRIDC (http://www.fmriddc.org), he was one of the core members responsible for bringing the Data Center online, the first publicly accessible repository of peer-reviewed fMRI studies. Throughout his career, I have been involved in enabling collaborative research, data sharing and discovery through the application of advanced informatics approaches. This started at USC with his involvement in the Human Brain Project and continues today with my work on NIF, dkNET and with standards bodies such as the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility. After transitioning to the University of California, San Diego, he was Executive Director of BIRN Coordinating Center which deployed an international collaborative network that supported hundreds of researchers and Terabytes of data spread across more than 30 institutions. He is a Principal Investigator for the Neuroscience Information Framework (NIF; http://neuinfo.org RRID:SCR_002894) and the NIDDK Information Network (dkNET; http://dknet.org RRID:SCR_001606). NIF and dkNET are open source information frameworks enabling researchers around the world to access a rich virtual environment identifying and providing access to domain-relevant data and resources, to advance scientific inquiry leading to new discoveries and treatments of human disease. This work is being further extended via the Open Data Commons for Spinal Cord Injury (ODC-SCI) which is developing a FAIR data platform for spinal cord injury researchers and is currently being launched on the extended SciCrunch framework. He is also a co-founder of SciCrunch, Inc. a technology start up based on technologies developed by NIF and dkNET.	0000-0001-5212-7052	The University of California at San Diego
Joseph Gum	Data Stewardship Coordinator	Mid	Joseph Gum is the NSF NCAR - The National Center for Atmospheric Research - Data Stewardship Coordinator. Previously he spent 2 years as the public face of repositories, data management, and open science. He curated data, wrote data management plans, and helped progress open and reproducible science at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography.	0000-0002-3045-0593	National Center for Atmospheric Research
Johanna Havemann	Director, Consultant and Trainer	Mid	Dr. Johanna Havemann is a trainer and consultant in Open Science Communication and digital Research Management. She is the founder and director of Access 2 Perspectives and co-founder of AfricArXiv, promoting open scholarly communication in Africa. With experience across NGOs, startups, and institutions like the UN Environment Programme, she supports researchers in developing effective communication and project management skills. Her work focuses on advancing global Open Science across Africa and Europe.	0000-0002-6157-1494	Access 2 Perspectives

Mike Hawrylycz	Investigator	Senior	Mike Hawrylycz joined the Allen Institute in 2003. He is responsible for the direction of the data analysis and annotation effort. Hawrylycz has worked in a variety of applied mathematics and computer science areas, addressing challenges in consumer and investment finance, electrical engineering and image processing, and computational biology and genomics. Hawrylycz received his Ph.D. in applied mathematics at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. He subsequently was a post-doctoral researcher in the Computer Research and Applications Group at the Los Alamos National Laboratory.	0000-0002-5741-8024	The Allen Institute
Deoyani Nandrekar Heinis	Programme Manager	Mid	I am a Sr. Data Scientist currently working at National Institute of Standards and Technology. I have over fifteen years experience working in scientific software design and development. In the past I worked for building and developing software for Astronomical data and data analysis and infrastructure projects. I am PMP certified project manager. I managed various software development projects to support scientific data in the past.	0000-0003-1201-033X	National Institute of Standards and Technology
Ashley Jester	Director, Research Data and Library Services	Mid	BA Political Science, Ph.D. Political Science. Dr. Jester has spent her post-graduate career in academic libraries, first working research data services and currently mid-career as a library director. Her work has centered advocacy for open science and reproducible research. Dr. Jester is a member of several professional organizations centered on research data and information services, and she serves on the Administrative Committee of the International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology (IASSIST).	0000-0003-1523-913X	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Daniel S. Katz	Chief Scientist, NCSA; Research Professor, CS & iSchool	Senior	Daniel S. Katz is Chief Scientist at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign and Research Associate Professor in the Siebel School of Computing and Data Science and the School of Information Sciences (iSchool). He is also a Better Scientific Software (BSSw) Fellow. Dan's interest is in the development and use of advanced cyberinfrastructure to solve challenging problems at multiple scales. His technical research interests are in applications, algorithms, fault tolerance, and programming in parallel and distributed computing, including HPC, Grid, Cloud, etc. He is also interested in policy issues, including citation and credit mechanisms and practices associated with software and data, organization and community practices for collaboration, and career paths for computing researchers. He is a senior member of the IEEE and ACM, a founding editor and current Associate Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Open Source Software, and a co-founder and the steering committee chair for the Research Software Alliance (ReSA).	0000-0001-5934-7525	University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
Erica Key	US Global Hub Director	Senior	Erica Key is the US Global Hub Director for Future Earth. Prior to joining the organization, she was the first Executive Director of the Belmont Forum and implemented an international open data policy and principles into transdisciplinary, transnational funding calls, with participation from more than 200 research programs. This work drew on her experience as a program director at the US National Science Foundation where she supported ethically accessible data, including repositories focused on Indigenous and Traditional Knowledge and pandisciplinary near real-time observations in CADIS. She has a research background that includes both remote sensing and shipboard data collected by sensors and human observers.	0000-0002-5099-5961	Future Earth
Danie Kinkade	Information Systems Specialist; Director, Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	Senior	Danie Kinkade is an Information Systems Specialist at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, where she serves as co-PI and Director of the Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO, an oceanographic research data repository). She holds a BS in Biology and Marine Science, an MSc in Marine Science, and possesses over 27 years experience managing oceanographic observational data. Her current research lies at the intersection of information and oceanographic sciences, where focus on data curation and publication using novel technologies and disciplinary best practices facilitates open science. She is active in efforts to advance the field of data management and has served in a leadership capacity for several geoscience data-related programs and consortia such as the US Council of Data Facilities, the NSF EarthCube Program, the Earth and Space Information Partners (ESIP), and the American Geophysical Union's Informatics Section, in addition to serving as an investigator on several grant sponsored cyberinfrastructure-related projects.	0000-0002-1134-7347	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute; Biological Chemical Oceanographic Data Management Office

Malgorzata (Losia) Lagisz	Research Fellow	Mid	PhD Biology. Lagisz is a Research Fellow at the University of New South Wales in Sydney. With prior appointments in the UK and New Zealand, her interdisciplinary research spans ecology, evolutionary biology, biomedical science, environmental studies, and social science. She specializes in evidence synthesis — systematic reviews, meta-analyses, systematic maps, and meta-epidemiology — to tackle critical questions across disciplines. Dr Lagisz co-leads a team dedicated to advancing evidence synthesis, Open Science and equity in research.	0000-0002-3993-6127	University of New South Wales Sydney, University of Alberta
Madison Langseth	IT Specialist/IT Architect	Mid	Madison Langseth is a science data manager at the U.S. Geological Survey. She develops tools and workflows to make the ScienceBase data release process more efficient for researchers and data managers.	0000-0002-4472-9106	U.S. Geological Survey
Kit Lewers	PhD Student	Early	Kit Lewers is a PhD student in Information Science and Interdisciplinary Quantitative Biology at the University of Colorado Boulder, focusing on sensor-derived environmental data and biodiversity informatics. My research explores optimizing data pipelines for remote sensing platforms like AVIRIS-NG, LiDAR, and various satellite datasets, applying advanced compression and analysis methods to improve Earth observation workflows. I aim to advance data interoperability across platforms such as NASA's BioSCape, GBIF, OBIS, and GEO BON through scalable, event-driven microservice architectures. With a professional background spanning software engineering, spatial analysis, and data science, I bridge technical development with ecological research. I am passionate about building modular, open-source tools that enhance environmental monitoring, data accessibility, and global biodiversity research. My current work includes developing APIs, serverless architectures, and dynamic data processing frameworks to transform complex environmental datasets into actionable insights.	0000-0003-0526-4075	University of Colorado
Jared Lyle	Archivist, Director of Curation Services	Senior	Jared Lyle is an Archivist at the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR), where he directs the Metadata and Preservation Unit, which is responsible for Metadata, the Bibliography of Data-Related Literature, and Digital Preservation. He also serves as Director of the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Alliance, an international membership organization that creates and maintains technical standards for describing research data in the social, demographic, economic, and health sciences. In addition to his roles at ICPSR, Jared is a member of the CoreTrustSeal Board, where he contributes to the development and promotion of standards of trustworthy data repositories.	0000-0001-8623-7612	University of Michigan, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research
Maryann Martone	Professor Emeritus (Neuroscience) University of California San Diego; Co-Founder SciCrunch Inc	Senior	BA from Wellesley College in Biological Psychology and Ancient Greek and her Ph. D. in Neuroscience from the University of California, San Diego. She is a professor Emerita at UCSD, but still maintains an active laboratory, the FAIR Data Informatics Lab. She started her career as a neuroanatomist, specializing in light and electron microscopy, but her main research for the past 20 years focused on informatics for neuroscience, i.e., neuroinformatics. She led the Neuroscience Information Framework (NIF), a national project to establish a uniform resource description framework for neuroscience, and the NIDDK Information Network (dknet), a portal for connecting researchers in digestive, kidney and metabolic disease to data, tools, and materials. Dr. Martone is past President of FORCE11, an organization dedicated to advancing scholarly communication and e-scholarship and served as Editor-in-Chief for Brain and Behavior for five years. She completed two years as the chair of the Council on Training, Science and Infrastructure for the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility and is now the chair of the Governing Board. Since retiring, she served as the Director of Biological Sciences for Hypothesis, a technology non-profit developing an open annotation layer for the web (2015-2018) and founded SciCrunch, a technology start up based on technologies developed by NIF and dkNET. Her current projects include dkNET, the Open Data Commons for Spinal Cord Injury, the Open Data Commons for Traumatic Brain Injury, the PRE Clinical Interagency Research Resource for TBI (PRECISE), SPARC (Stimulating Peripheral Activity to Relieve Conditions), Re-JOIN and PRECISION HEAL and ReproNIM.	0000-0002-8406-3871	The University of California at San Diego

Leah McEwen	Chemistry Librarian	Senior	Leah McEwen is the Chemistry Librarian at Cornell University where she has supported information discovery and scholarly communication in the chemical sciences since 1999. She is an active contributor to national and international chemical information initiatives, organizing dozens of thematic programs on research documentation and dissemination. She has served as both Secretary and Program Chair for the ACS Division of Chemical Information, and on the ACS Joint Board-Council Committees on Publishing, Ethics and Chemical Safety. She is a founding chair of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Chemistry Research Data Interest Group (DIG Chemistry) and a board member of the International Chemical Identifier - InChI Trust. She currently serves as chair of the IUPAC Committee on Publications and Cheminformatics Data Standards to facilitate design and implementation of digital standards. She is lead on the Chemistry case study for the CODATA-RDA WorldFAIR Initiative to advance FAIR data practices and is an international advisor for the NFDI4Chem research data infrastructure consortium in Germany. She holds master's degrees in Nutritional Biochemistry from Cornell University and Library and Information Science from Emporia State University and was the first Paul Olet - Eugene Garfield Fellow at the Science History Institute.	0000-0003-2968-1674	Cornell University
Nokuthula Mchunu	Deputy Director at the African Open Science Platform	Senior	Dr. Nokuthula Mchunu holds the position of Deputy Director at the African Open Science Platform, which is hosted by the National Research Foundation in South Africa. With extensive expertise in academic outreach initiatives, science popularization, and the implementation of STEM activities within local communities, she previously served as a senior researcher at the Agricultural Research Council of South Africa in the Biotechnology Platform. Dr. Mchunu earned her doctoral degree in fungal genomics and spent over 15 years as a senior scholar in the Department of Biotechnology at Durban University of Technology. Throughout her career, she has contributed as a scientist in various international institutions, including the University of Cincinnati (USA), Lund University (Sweden), Tianjin University (China), and the Centre for Chemical Biology (Malaysia). Dr. Mchunu holds the distinction of being the inaugural recipient of the Young Scientist Programme established between China and South Africa. Her research encompasses diverse areas such as Covid and pathogen surveillance in wastewater, fungal genetics, Cannabis, and African legume genomics.	0000-0001-5156-9457	National Research Foundation South Africa
Fiona Murphy	Co-founder, Partnerships & Community Development	Senior	A founder member of the MoreBrains Cooperative Consulting team, Fiona is a research/data/publishing consultant. Previously: After completing a DPhil in English Literature, Fiona held a range of scholarly publishing roles with Oxford University Press, Bloomsbury Academic and Wiley. As Publisher for Earth and Environmental Sciences at Wiley, she began to specialise in emerging scholarly communications with particular emphasis on Open Science and Open Data. She ran her own company, Murphy Mitchell Consulting for over five years before teaming up with Josh Brown, Phill Jones and Alice Meadows to form MoreBrains.	0000-0003-1693-1240	MoreBrains Cooperative Consulting
Jiban K. Pal	Scientific and Technical Professional (Senior Grade), ISI; Founding Member, Re3data Editorial Board	Mid	Jiban K. PAL (IND, b.1972): is an information specialist, a habilitated sociologist of science, and a founding member of the Re3data Editorial Board. He earned his Ph.D. in Scientometrics and was a Visiting Fellow at ICTP-Trieste, Italy. He has been serving at the Indian Statistical Institute for more than 20 years. He also acts as a Nodal Officer for the Indian Research Information Network System, Government of India. He is an elected member of both the FORCE11 Board of Directors and the ISI Governing Council. His areas of interest include Metadata engineering, Research data management, Open Science, and Scientometrics.	0000-0002-2870-9180	Indian Statistical Institute
Micaela Parker	Executive Director	Senior	Micaela Parker is the Founder and Executive Director of the Academic Data Science Alliance (ADSA), a professional association for academic data science and AI leaders, practitioners, and educators. Through collaborative events and community-driven resource development, ADSA's networks of academic leaders advance data science and AI best practices in research, education, and training. Before launching ADSA, Micaela was Executive Director for the University of Washington's eScience Institute. She has authored several papers offering guidance for emerging data science initiatives. Micaela earned her PhD in UW's School of Oceanography working on large data projects bridging oceanography and genomics.	0000-0003-1007-4612	Academic Data Science Alliance, a project of Community Initiatives 501(c)(3)

Marianne Peiffer	Editor, Journalist, Copywriter	Mid	Dr. Marianne Peiffer is an academic editor at INRAE (France's National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment). She completed her doctorate at INRAE in forest ecology. She leads the development of peer review for data papers since she began as data editor in 2014 for the journal <i>Annals of Forest Science</i> (https://annforsci.biomedcentral.com/). Moreover, she is leading the journal <i>Apidologie</i> dedicated on the biology of bees (https://link.springer.com/journal/13592). She is also interested in policy issues, in particular the open dissemination of research results. More specifically, she is implementing mechanisms that benefit the career paths of researchers by developing the use of infrastructures.	0000-0001-5326-3590	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
Ge Peng	Chief Research Scientist	Senior	Dr. Ge Peng is a Chief Research Scientist at Science Systems and Applications, Inc., with expertise in Earth science modeling and data analysis, management, and stewardship. With a Ph.D in meteorology, her work focuses on long-term Earth system trends and advancing data stewardship and governance at NASA, NOAA, and WMO. She currently chairs NASA's O'FAIR Working Group and the WMO Expert Team on Information Management, and serves as an At-Large Member of the ESIP Board and an external advisory board member for an EU Horizon 2 project – Supporting and Standardising Climate Services in Europe and Beyond. Formerly, she was a Chief Editor of <i>Earth System Science Data</i> .	0000-0002-1986-9115	Science Systems and Applications, Inc.
Yuhan "Douglas" Rao	Senior Research Scholar	Early	Dr. Yuhan "Douglas" Rao is a Senior Research Scholar with NC State University specializing in AI for earth science applications. He received his PhD in geographical sciences from University of Maryland. His research focuses on remote sensing, climate modeling and analysis, and advanced statistical modeling. He currently co-chairs the World Climate Research Programme Earth System Modeling and Observations Project's Working Group on Observations for Researching Climate. He also serves as the Vice President for Earth Science Information Partners.	0000-0001-6850-3403	North Carolina State University
Nihar Shah	Associate Professor	Early	Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science. His research uses human-AI collaboration to address fundamental questions about scientific work: Is the research correct? Is it high-quality? Is it fundable, or even authentic? His research has already been used in the evaluation of over 100,000 research papers and thousands of grant proposals. Beyond science, the challenges his research addresses extend naturally into other domains, and the algorithms we have developed are also deployed in diverse applications such as admissions decisions and competition judging.	0000-0001-5158-9677	Carnegie Mellon University
Adam Shepherd	Technical Director	Senior	Adam Shepherd is the Technical Director for the Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO) located at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution where he has worked as a software developer since 2000. He serves as co-chair of the Vocabulary Services and Semantics Interest Group for the Research Data Alliance. Currently, his work focuses on data semantics for improved discovery and reuse.	0000-0003-4486-9448	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Susan Shingledecker	Executive Director	Senior	Susan Shingledecker serves as Executive Director of Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP), a diverse community of Earth and environmental data professionals working to empower innovative use and stewardship of data to solve our planet's greatest challenges. She has a passion for data driven solutions and comes to data management from an applied perspective having worked in conservation, the insurance industry, state government and on Capitol Hill. Susan brings to ESIP over a decade of nonprofit management experience with both national and regional organizations and a diverse 20 year career in the environmental field spanning international consulting, federal and state public policy, outdoor recreation and conservation experience. Susan holds a Master of Environmental Management with a focus on natural resources economics and policy from Duke University and a Bachelor of Arts in international studies from American University.		Earth Science Information Partners

Martina Stockhause	IPCC DDC Manager	Senior	Martina Stockhause is a Senior Data Manager at the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ). Her current role focuses on the development and implementation of federated research infrastructures, which includes the joint management of the IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC) and providing the data citation component for a federated climate research infrastructure. She contributes her expertise to expert groups including the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP), DataCite's Community Engagement EMEA Expert Group and the IPCC Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data). She has served as Earth and Space Science Informatics (ESSI) Deputy Division President in the European Geosciences Union (EGU). Martina has been a member of the RDA since its inception and has contributed to a number of Interest/Working Groups.	0000-0001-6636-4972	DKRZ / IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC)
Andrea Thomer	Associate Professor	Mid	Andrea Thomer is an associate professor of information at the University of Michigan School of Information. She conducts research in the areas of data curation, museum informatics, earth science and biodiversity informatics, information organization, and computer supported cooperative work. She is especially interested in how people use and create data and metadata; the impact of information organization on information use; issues of data provenance, reproducibility, and integration; and long-term data curation and infrastructure sustainability. She is studying a number of these issues through the "Migrating Research Data Collections" project – a recently awarded Laura Bush 21st Century Librarianship Early Career Research Grant from the Institute of Museum and Library Services. Dr. Thomer received her doctorate in Library and Information Science from the School of Information Sciences at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign in 2017.	0000-0001-6238-3498	University of Michigan
Carol Thompson	Associate Director, Data & Technology	Mid	One of the architects of the Allen Mouse Brain Atlas, she oversaw from concept to execution, the Allen Developing Mouse Brain Atlas, a resource characterizing gene expression from the embryonic brain to the adult, and the Sleep Study, a resource that explores the many dynamic changes in gene expression induced by sleep deprivation. Beyond that, Carol has managed the build of integrated pipelines for high throughput generation of biological datasets, including hardware and software integration for neurophysiology, including calcium imaging and Neuropixels silicon probes, as well as for transcriptomics profiling and stem cell engineering, culminating in freely available community resources for neuroscience. As the Program and Project Manager, she has supported the creation of the Allen Brain Observatory, a data resource for cellular physiological responses to visual input, and its sister project, OpenScope, which generates datasets based on proposals from the community. Carol is interested in the power of projects that lie at the intersection of big data, biology and computation. She is currently responsible for coordinating the data ecosystem for community-generated data as part of the BRAIN Initiative Cell Census Network (BICCN) and for BRAIN Initiative Cell Atlas Network (BICAN), and is also responsible for consortium administration. Carol holds a BS in Biology from the University of Richmond and a Ph.D. in Biochemistry from the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, where she studied cryptochromes under the guidance of Nobel laureate Aziz Sancar, M.D., Ph.D.	0000-0003-1528-3237	The Allen Institute
Lesley Wyborn	Honorary Professor	Senior	Lesley Wyborn is an Honorary Professor at the Australian National University and works part time for the Australian Research Data Commons. She had 42 years' experience in Geoscience Australia in Earth science research and in data science/data management. Her current research focusses on enabling Open Science practices including versioning, reproducibility and operationalising FAIR and CARE. She is a participant in many global informatics initiatives.	0000-0001-5976-4943	National Computational Infrastructure, AuScope